

THE ROLE OF MARKETING ACTIVITY CONCEPTS IN THE FIELD OF CONSTRUCTION MARKET SERVICES

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Abstract. *In this article, the goal of construction for consumers, the justification of the socio-economic importance of the formation of the market of construction services, and the marketing concept chosen by construction marketing employees in their activities are considered.*

Keywords: *construction market, service, marketing concept, strategy, labor productivity.*

INTRODUCTION. Today, the most urgent issues facing construction materials manufacturing enterprises are to fundamentally improve productivity, increase the quality of construction materials, and increase the competitiveness of construction materials. In our country, while paying great attention to raising the standard of living of the population, solving social issues and ensuring economically stable development, supporting young families materially and morally is considered as one of the priority tasks. Different strata of the population, especially the youth, are socially supported. In the process of further liberalization and deepening of economic reforms in our republic, effective construction services are being formed and developing.

Research methodology. Systematic approach, abstract-logical thinking, grouping, comparison, factor analysis, selective observation methods were used in the research process.

Analysis and results. In the conditions of the world financial and economic crisis, the issues of justifying the ways of using the opportunities of marketing organization in the activity of the construction and production enterprises of the Samarkand region have been thoroughly studied. It advances the tasks under the implementation of the objectives:

- justification of the socio-economic importance of the formation of the construction services market in Uzbekistan under the conditions of the world financial and economic crisis;
- choosing a research object and studying its economic activity;
- To study the role of construction and production enterprises of Samarkand region in economic development;
- conducting an analysis of marketing activities in construction and making appropriate recommendations;
- development of marketing strategies for building a portfolio of construction products and services.

Kurilish's marketing employees work on the basis of their chosen marketing concept.

The concept of marketing activity is the philosophy and strategy of the construction aimed at consumers. It is based on the analysis of the total indicators of construction, which affect the economic and quality and speed of construction. On the basis of the marketing concept, optimization of construction activities is formed, and then its external and internal activities are comprehensively planned.

A certain marketing concept is chosen depending on the characteristics of the constructions (large and small, originality of activity, founder), purpose and tasks. Some of the constructions have been using a certain concept for many years under Russian conditions. Some constructions change their concepts immediately depending on external and internal factors.

Let's look at the marketing concept used in construction business.

1. **Concept of production or improvement of construction technology.** This means that when customers choose a builder, they choose a builder who provides an acceptable service at a low price, while the construction market often offers traditional services with high efficiency.

This concept is chosen by construction markets in the following cases:

- a) if the majority of actual and potential customers have a low income;
- b) reduction of fixed and fixed costs of construction based on the increase of the customer base, provides an increase in funds allocated to some services in the market of construction services.

2. **The concept of goods, that is, the concept of improving construction services.** This means attracting customers to construction services that are superior in terms of their characteristics and quality to their competitors, and on this basis bring more benefits to consumers. Constructions in this case focus on improving the quality of services provided.

This marketing concept is based on the quality level of construction services provided, consideration of the political and economic conditions affecting the quality of services, reduction of risks when construction services are provided.

3. **The concept of trade, or the concept of intensification of commercial activity.** It consists in organizing advertising of construction services and an active information system in order to increase the required level of customers and the volume of services provided based on marketing research.

A typical example of this concept is the establishment of insurance and leasing companies, pension funds, as well as non-traditional services (know-how, consultations in various areas of business, etc.) Buildings to implement this concept form a multi-functional marketing service.

4. **Traditional Marketing Concept:** it is possible to provide an increase in consumer demand for construction services, mainly based on the analysis of the consumption and demand motivation of certain social groups of the population. In other words, marketing should start with the analysis of demand and supply for one or another construction services, and only after that, it should consist of developing a program for moving the supply. This concept began to gain its supporters in the framework of construction in the mid-1990s. This concept is characterized by:

- a) increase in demand for traditional construction services;
- b) availability of external and internal infrastructure in most buildings;
- c) development of the state and international financial market;
- g) limited monetary resources.

The general relationship of the four listed marketing concepts can be expressed graphically (Chart 29).

Here, axis S1 represents the satisfaction of the interests of construction customers; And the S2 axis represents the interest of the construction itself. Dividing buildings into four quadrants is of great importance in order to determine the degree of danger to them. On this basis, tactics and strategies for working with specific and potential customers are developed.

Figure 1. General relationship of marketing concepts

In the first quadrant, it is possible to include constructions that satisfy the interest of customers with a certain level of profit. These constructions take the first place in the stability (reliability) rating. This is included in the quadrant

constructions provide customers with comprehensive services at a high quality level. Customers of these buildings are also considered financially stable.

The second quadrant includes constructions whose clients are not sufficiently stable in the market of construction services. For this reason, customers pay more for specific construction services than for other constructions. In this quadrant, in most cases, there are those who want to get high profits without spending too much on construction technology. Constructions stay in this quadrant in most cases for two years, after which such constructions lose their respect in the business world and in the eyes of customers.

From the third to the quadrant - In the course of construction, constructions fail to fulfill their contractual obligations due to economic and marketing shortcomings of constructions or due to the decrease in the value of securities purchased by constructions.

In the fourth quadrant - in most cases, constructions that introduce new technologies at the expense of a construction loan, change the assortment policy, increase the volume of production without studying the market demand, and generally favor the customers can be included.

This quadrant also includes facilities that provide loans to customers who produce goods for children, the elderly, the sick, and the disabled.

5. Social-ethical concept. This concept indicates that the purposeful philosophy, idea, policy and strategy of construction is not focused on the interests of narrow sectors, but on the interests of the whole human, the whole community. Sometimes this concept is also referred to as "Human-centered" or "Intellectual consumption concept". This concept is considered to be the most promising concept for construction and focuses on ensuring the interest of society.

This concept was formed in the early 1980s. One of the variants of this concept is the "7-S" concept (Figure 30). Here, the interests of consumers, producers and society are aligned with the help of marketing instruments. Or in other words, in the process of meeting the demand of the customers, the construction receives its benefits, and the society (through the construction and the customers) receives its contribution in the form of budget allocations or construction of social facilities.

All elements of the "7-S" system have a specific content, they are variable and depend on various external and internal factors. For buildings, their full implementation requires a lot of material costs.

Now let's look at the elements of the "7-S" system.

S1 is a construction customer or a construction service consumer. Any development can only survive if there are consumers of its services. Construction in the market and meets the consumer. The peculiarity of the financial market is that its main subjects are closely connected with each other, the relationship between them is clear, but depends on many factors.

Increasing competition between constructions requires special attention to the problems of establishing relations with each customer, establishing cooperative relations between constructions and customers. This, in turn, is a guarantee of winning the competition.

S2 - personnel, i.e. construction, is an element that connects customers and competitors. The level of effective operation of any construction depends to a large extent on the skills of personnel and their attitude to their work. The main challenge for construction here is recruiting and gathering information about leading customers and competitors.

S3 – communication. This means the forms and methods of conveying the main construction ideas and specific measures of one or another service to the consumers of construction services. S3 - includes four issues.

S3.1 – technical support of communication (television, radio, internet, etc.).

S3.2 - the completeness of information about the subject of the contract, the construction service and its description, the procedure for providing construction services for consumers, clients. This information should mainly answer 5 main questions: When? How? Where? To whom? how much A construction service employee should not get into a dead end when making a deal with customers, he will need to carry the deal through to the end with great urgency.

S3.3 - to clearly and clearly state the purpose. This situation saves time and helps to increase the efficiency of the activity.

S4 - coordination, i.e. the existence of direct and reverse relations in the activity of objects and subjects of the construction organization.

S5 – quality: a set of service characteristics that can meet the needs of certain customers. It is one of the key elements that ensure the prosperity of any manufacturer as well as the development and customers.

S6 - competition: it is a process of struggle and cooperation between producers and consumers for profitable conditions to achieve their goals. To determine the competitiveness of certain goods (services), it is appropriate to analyze indicators such as price, production costs, and profit. The high level of competitiveness of the manufactured product (service) is closely related to the unparalleled quality of products and services.

S7 – culture: includes all the above-mentioned components of the system and represents the level of development of society, as well as certain layers.

The model of marketing activities using the "7-S" concept of constructions is multi-dimensional and socially oriented.

The "7-S" marketing concept is a systematic philosophy of construction business, as it involves the collection, processing and analysis of a large amount of information about construction activities. Of course, such constructions will have some competitive advantages over constructions that do not have complete information. However, obtaining such information requires a large amount of expenses and qualified personnel.

Today, each of these concepts is used to one degree or another in the field of finance and construction services.

The main functions of construction marketing are:

- 1) a comprehensive study of the construction services market and its requirements and forecasting its future development;
- 2) realistic assessment of production-sale, export and other possibilities of constructions;
- 3) development of a long-term marketing strategy, indicating its purpose, tasks, ways of implementation;
- 4) planning construction policy based on market demand and construction potential;
- 5) demand formation and sales promotion;
- 6) sales planning and organization.

The introduction of these functions creates conditions for improving the economic activity of buildings.

Thus, construction marketers are required to know the modern methods of managing marketing activities in order to overcome the crisis situations that may occur in the construction services market and in the economy.

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